

PARENT-TEACHER CONSULTATION FOR LEARNERS AT-RISK: ITS EFFECT TO THE ROLES OF PARENTS AND LEARNERS' OUTCOMES

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Parent-Teacher Consultation for Learners At-Risk: Its Effect to the Roles of Parents and Learners' Outcomes

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Abstract

The researchers investigated the effects of conducting Parent-Teacher Consultation to the roles of parents and outcomes among the identified Learners at-Risks of Nagpayong High School from school year 2021-2022. Respondents were section advisers, learners at-risks and the learners at-risks' parents who were selected based on their availability and willingness to participate in this study. Mixed method was utilized to obtain answers to the research questions using researcher-made questionnaires and semi-structured interviews. The results revealed the teachers-initiated teacher-parent conference (PTC) through distance communication, face-to-face meeting, other means of communication and exerted interventions. Then, findings were positively manifested in the effects of PTC to the roles of parents. Results also revealed that parents modelled positive attitudes, did monitoring, got involved academically, collaborated with the school, and motivated the learners; however, it also exposed leniency among parents as they still allow their children to skip classes and play mobile games despite their school responsibilities. Also, giving rewards is not highly practiced by parents. Students also narrated learning experiences such as Home-related factors, Lack of Resources, Leisure as Distraction, and Learning Behaviour and Attitude as the perceived causes of their poor performances. Conducting PTC was believed to affect their feelings, actions and relationship with their parents. Also, teachers expressed home-related factors, lack of interest, lack of resources and dishonesty that caused them problems in conducting PTC. On the other hand, teachers' responses about the effects of PTC were categorized into positive and negative: parents' active participation, realization of the needs, consistent monitoring, learners' active participation, understanding of rules, strengthened communication and relationship, parent's positive response and increased passing rate are the unfolded positive effects; while too much consideration, habitual actions, low quality of learners and blaming teachers are the conveyed negative effects. Lastly, the researchers extracted recommendations for teacher's involvement, school administration support, and parents' motivation.

Keywords: *parent-teacher consultation, learners at risk, learner's outcomes*

Introduction

For the past few years, the role of parents in the learners' life has been an overlooked factor in education. Many teachers would agree that most of the time they were blamed and perceived to lack competence regarding learners' poor performance. For instance, relative to Sen. Sonny Angara's Senate Bill 2312, he made mention that "The quality of education is closely linked to the competency of teachers. If we want to produce the best students, then we should start by providing them with the best teachers."

The role of parents has always been vital in a child's development. Education Bureau (2018) contends that parents must be (1) school partners who play an active role in their children's education and supporting school-related activities, (2) school clients who understand the kind of education provided to their children and how it works, (3) school decision makers who put forward views about what the school is doing and make suggestions on how it should be run, and (4) home educators who provide basic care and guidance towards the good behavior and general development of their children.

In 2020, the world was faced with the challenge of living amidst the life-threatening nature of CoVid19 Virus. This health-related issue breeds problems to all other sectors such as in the economy, business, agriculture, and even in education (Chriscaden, 2020).

Limited mobility due to the extended lockdowns is a preeminence for the Department of Education to implement Distance Learning through alternative learning delivery modes namely blended, modular, text-based, and online learning. However, despite the persistent effort of the government and teachers to bridge education to the learners, many students are still failing to achieve the expected learning standards.

Even before the pandemic, absenteeism among learners was already rampant and considered a major factor of learners' poor performances in schools. Several interventions are already laid down and have been conducted to address this problem, anyhow, this issue of absenteeism and poor compliance has become even worse in the new delivery modes where teachers do not directly interact with learners. Thus, the role of parents had been highlighted and regarded with a need to be intensified.

In lieu of these problems and realizations, Parent-Teacher Consultation is recognized as an indispensable intervention to improve learners' performance, especially those who are considered as Learners At-Risk. Based on Waterford.org (2018), the most accurate predictor of academic achievement is the extent to which families encourage learning at home and the parent's involvement in their children's education. Parent's engagement on learners' school lives not only reinforces the child's motivation to comply with academic requirements. Moreso, it promotes love for lifelong learning.

In the Philippines, home-visitation has become a trend among educators. A study conducted by Gatilogo and Tan (2019) revealed that students agree that their teachers' home visitation is practiced from the second quarter until the end of the school year 2017-2018. It also indicated that when instructors do home visitation to pupils it signifies teachers' care, and it motivates parents to take more of an active role in the learning activities of their children.

Likewise, based on the reports through the monitoring form of Learners At-Risk in Nagpayong High School, data shows that there are one-hundred ten (110) LARS in Grade 12 and sixty-four (64) LARS in Grade 11. It also presented some of the actions taken by the teachers to aid these learners such as chat-based and video conferencing with parents, utilization of call slip and home visitation. However, at the end of first semester, the summary report shows that only 71 or 65.4 % of Grade 12 LARs and 18 or 28.13% of Grade 11 LARs were retained for second semester enrolment.

As class advisers who often conduct Teacher-Parent Consultations, the researchers are motivated in advocating a strengthened parental role in the education process. This study aims to answer how Teacher -Parents Consultations are conducted and how it affects parental roles and student outcomes. It also has the intention to elicit teachers' perspective on the effectiveness of Teacher-Parent Consultations based on the compliance rate and passing rate of learners. Hopefully, this study would provide insights in developing parents-teachers partnership and help improve learners at-risk's academic performance.

Research Questions

This study focused on Teacher-Parents Consultations, its methods and its effects on parental roles and students' outcomes. Specifically, it seeks to answer the following questions:

1. What techniques/strategies did the teachers use to conduct teacher-parent consultation?
2. What are the effects of TPC to the roles of parents in terms of:
 - 2.1. modelling positive attitude;
 - 2.2. monitoring;
 - 2.3. school coordination;
 - 2.4. communication and motivation; and
 - 2.5. academic involvement?
3. What are the problems encountered by the learners that contributed to their poor academic performance?
4. How did the Learners-At-Risk perceive the effects of Parent-Teacher Conference?
5. What are the problems encountered by teachers in conducting Parent-Teacher Conference?
6. How did the teachers perceive the effect of Parent-Teacher Conference?
7. What recommendations are drawn out from the respondents?

Literature Review

According to Horton (2015), "at-risk" students are those who regarded as having a higher likelihood of academic failure or dropping out of school. The term may be applied to students who face circumstances or characteristics (factors) that could jeopardize their ability to achieve academic goals or complete school, such as homelessness, incarceration, teenage pregnancy, serious health issues, domestic violence, or transiency, or it may refer to learning disabilities, low test scores, disciplinary problems, grade retentions, or other learning related factors that could adversely affect the educational performance and attainment of some students.

In this connection, teacher-parent consultation promotes partnership between parents and teachers to collaborate in helping the learners to achieve academic success. Teacher-parent consultation should be used as a platform to make a lasting bond with the parent to increase the likelihood of academic success for their child. Teacher parent consultation should not be used as a venue to acknowledge the flaws and inabilities of students, but as a stepping stone to foster improvement within each child ("Parent Teacher Conference", 2022).

Likewise, parent involvement is a term researchers use to describe the interest family takes in a child's education, is of special interest to educators who encourage parents to help learners at home with homework and projects. School districts also focus on methods to encourage parents to view the school as an important part of family life as children grow (Ryan, 2018).

Relatively, as stated by Jeynes (2011), the study of parental involvement is far more different from the previous research conducted that is needed to have a further study. He said that the parental involvement theory has a wide range that differs from the preceding proposed theories.

Moreso, Boonk, et al. (2018) explained that parents' involvement has an indirect relationship to the students' academic attainment. Although they contribute a lot in enhancing the students' learning capacities, succeeding will still be based on students' application of parents' learning support in their studies. They also stated that there are variables and factors influencing the students, such as parents' enthusiasm and expectation because building up high aspiration on students' academic performance shows positive impact on their learning outcomes.

Furthermore, Marshall & Jackman, (2015) revealed that parental involvement has a beneficial connection between parental

involvement and student participation. Parent involvement is composed of four ranges, including parental illustration, parental instruction, parental motivation, and parental supplementing. The four components are positively connected to each other, specifically in active involvement. It also states that students' academic outcome possesses higher benefits when parents are involved.

Lastly, Moroni (2015) claimed that parental involvement has widened its range over the past years, but theories about these issues continue to change as methods and strategies are discovered. The authors decided to conduct a study which tackles parental involvement in terms of homework because according to them, it's the most questioned and considered as the emphasis of parents' learning involvement. It is said that when the parents are often helping the students in their homework without noticing that the learners are unable to cope up due to lack of parental strategies, academic achievement of the students fails.

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed mixed-research method. It is a method where both qualitative and quantitative approach are used to achieve answers to research questions. Descriptive-quantitative approach was utilized to answer understand the effects of Parent-Teacher Conference to the role of parents. While Phenomenology was applied to draw out answers about the specific teachers' approaches, problems and suggestions in conducting PTC, and learner's reasons for having poor performance and effects of PTC.

Respondents

Respondents were section advisers, learners at-risks and the learners at-risks' parents who were selected based on their availability and willingness to participate in this study.

Instrument

There were three research instruments used in this study. The questionnaire for parents consists of 2 parts. Part 1 is a 4-Likert Scale survey questionnaire that will be used to identify effects of the Role of Parents after PTC. The role of parents is categorized according to Modelling positive attitude, Monitoring, School Coordination, Communication and Motivation, and Academic Involvement. Each item-statement from this questionnaire will be validated by the teachers prior to the distribution of the instrument to the target respondents. Part 2 is an essay type questionnaire for the parents' recommendations regarding PTC. The second was the guided interview for Learners-At-Risk to elicit themes regarding the effects of PTC to the learner outcomes. A guided interview focusing on their Motivation, Compliance, Student-Teacher Relationship, Student- Parent Relationship, and their recommendations about PTC.

The third was questionnaire for teachers which consists of 4 parts. Part 1 is a checklist type questionnaire that show the varied TPC methods conducted by teachers; Part 2 is a fill in the table item where teachers will write the number of LARs in their section, number of compliance and number LARs who completed the semester to get the compliance rate and passing rate of their advisory sections; Part 3 is a short response essay item for their reflection about the compliance rate and passing rate of their advisory; lastly, Part 4 is another short response essay for their recommendations about PTC.

Results and Discussion

This portion presents the results and discussion based on the gathered data.

Teachers' Techniques/Strategies Used to Conduct Parent-Teacher Consultation

Distance Communication

The first theme is Distance Communication which includes the following codes, Messenger, Phone Call, and Online Meeting.

As reflected on the interview, the first code, "Messenger" which was the most reoccurring answer from participant 1, "...contackin sila via messenger...", participant 2, "...first month na di umattend, kinontact agad si bata...kavideo call...", participant 4, "...Homevisit...messenger...pm personal message...", participant 5, "...yung parents nagrereply through gc o di kaya tatawagan ko sila via messenger...", participant 6, "...pinaka-convenient that time is through messenger...", so as participant 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, and 14. The Second code, "Online Meeting" was extracted from the responses of participant 5, "...gumamit tayo ng Zoom yung platform na Google meet o di kaya Zoom...halimbawa Zoom nagkaconduct tayo every quarter ng every parent-teacher na Card Day...". The third code, "Phone Call", was based on the responses of participant 6, "...kinucontact sila through personal messages. Iniisa isa ko na...", participant 7, "...Tinawagan ko rin sila ng personal sa kanilang mga cellphone...", participant 9, "...second number in personal number...", and participant 10, "...tumatawag tapos iniisa isa yung mga missed output nila..."

King (2021) on her blog exclaimed that to maintain parent-teacher connectedness during pandemic, the following platforms can be used for meaningful communication, Messaging Apps which provide immediate feedback and allow those with internet connectivity issues to gain access to videos and lessons posted on an online platform. One example is the Facebook Messenger. Another is emails, school websites and social media are ways in which parents can view happenings in the school, instructions that can be printed. An example of it is the school's Facebook page.

Face-to-face Meeting

The second emerging theme is Face-to-face Meeting which was themed after the codes, Home Visitation, Personal Meeting, and Card Distribution Day.

The second emerging theme, Face-to-face Meeting was generated from the participants' responses. Most of the responses reflected the code, Home Visitation which was generated from participant 1, "...pinuntahan...magkakasama kami nyan e na pumunta by group para lang puntahan yung mga studyante at parents ...", participant 2, "...home visitation for these three students...", participant 4, "...Homevisit...messenger...pm personal message...", participant 5, 6, 8, 11, 13, & 15. The second code, Personal Meeting was identified from the responses of participant 1, "...kinausap ko mismo sa guidance office...", participant 3, "...pinatawag yung bata...heart to heart talk with students tapos documented or pinasusulat....", participant 6, "...papunta lang dito (school) tyaka home visit kase iba paden yung kausap mo talaga yung magulang ...", participant 11, "...tinatawagan to meet face-to-face...", and participant 14, "...pinapapunta dito (school) iyong parents personally or yung guardian para mas makausap about doon sa concern sa kanilang anak...". The last code, Card Distribution Day was identified from the answers of participant 6, "...tinitake advantage ko kung may mga opportunities na na pupunta ang parents dito for example bigayan ng food packs...kumpleto sila eh kase meron silang nakukuha...card giving...", and participant 13, "...sinasabay during distribution of cards...".

Pascual (2019) reiterated in his study, DepEd Order No. 2, series of 2015, entitled Guidelines on the Establishment and Implementation of the- Results-Based Performance Management System (RPMS) in the Department of Educationl highlights the use of- Individual Performance Commitment and Review Forml which evaluates teacher's performance once a school year. For Teachers I, II and III positions, it can be seen under School, Home and Community Involvement area that the teacher is expected to visit 3% of the students in his class.

Parent-Teacher Communications

The third theme, Parent-Teacher Conference Communications was applied to the following codes: Call Slip, and Stakeholders' Participation.

The code such as Call Slip was drawn from the responses of participant 1, "...call slip...oo...pinuntahan...magkakasama kami nyan e na pumunta by group para lang puntahan yung mga studyante at parents...", participant 3, "...call slip with the help of SPTA to distribute the letter...", participant 6, "...nagpa-call slip ako so sinulatan ko yung mga parents...", participant 9, 12, & 15. While the code, Stakeholders' Participation was reflected from the following responses of participant 6, "...kasama mo yung Guidance advocate so hinde lang ikaw yung nag papaliwanag nandyan si ser dany para tulungan ka na ipaliwanag yung consequence...", participant 7, "...nagpadala ako ng sulat, sa pamamagitan ng SPTA, pinahatid ko sa kapitbahay, pinarecieve ko sa mga guardian...", participant 9, "...kapitbahay na yung kinall ko para macall ko yung attention ng parent...gumamit na ako ng third person pa para macontact, effective naman...", and participant 14, "...nagtatanong ako sa iba kong students kung sino yung nakakakilala or malapit na bahay...pinapapunta ko doon...pinagtitake ko ng pictures na nagbibigay ako don sa estudyante ko ng letter tapos pinapapicturan ko na binigay niya talaga doonsa parents...para hindi rin sila nagdadahilan na wala silang natanggap...".

Gatilogo and Tan (2019) pointed out on their study that home visit is a way to bridge the gap between school and home for students, families and teachers. Many studies suggest the importance of strong parental support on their children's learning at home. Parent-teacher conferences, phone calls, sending letters and progress reports are part of the communications to follow up students especially those who are academically at-risk to monitor their school performances and daily classroom behaviors.

Teachers' Intervention

The last theme, Teachers' Intervention was themed to the following codes: Intervention, Ultimatum, and Agreement.

The last theme was Teachers' Intervention. The first code is Intervention which was obtained from the responses of participant 1, "...pinapasok na natin yung mga mag iinternvetion ...", participant 7, "..., hinanda ko yung mga documents na kakailanganin sa pakikipagusap doon sa mga magulang, record specially, kulang ng bata ...", participant 10, & 15. The next code, Ultimatum was drawn from the responses of participant 1, "...yung tatay e binigyan ko ng ultimatum pag hindi...pwede akong bumalik ...sila na ang pumunta sa bahay para dun na kami sa harap mismo nag usap...", participant 6, "...may mga pananakot rin ako sa kanila...kailangan takutin para pumunta sila...", and participant 15, "...yung hindi talaga ma'am binigyan namin ng ultimatum...". The third code, Agreement was extracted from the responses of participant 2, "...agreement...home visitation for these three students...", participant 3, "...letter (kasunduan) with ID picture...", participant 6, "...kasama yung kasunduan? Opo...documented dapat...".

Interventions are activities that you would use to help students become successful in their classwork or decrease negative behavior towards others. This should be decided by both teacher and parent as a team (Grant, 2021).

Effects of Parent-Teacher Conference to the Roles of Parents

The table shows the extent of the roles of parents in online education in terms of modelling positive attitude, and it gained an overall weighted mean of 3.22 verbally interpreted as Agree. This finding shows that after the conduct of PTC, parents were able to show positive attitudes about online learning and model it to their children. They would want their children to have the outlook in online

education to be similar to what they had in face-to-face, that includes being positive despite the challenges they encounter in the new normal set-up.

Table 1. *Roles of Parents in Online Education: Model Positive Attitude*

<i>Roles of Parents in Online Education: Model Positive Attitude</i>		<i>Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
1.	I show my child positive outlook about online learning.	3.26	Strongly Agree
2.	I encouraged my child to take online classes seriously, similar to face-to-face classes.	3.50	Strongly Agree
3.	I show high expectations about learning through internet.	3.08	Agree
4.	I tell my child positive things about this COVID 19 Pandemic.	3.26	Strongly Agree
5.	I understand how my child feels during online classes	3.34	Strongly Agree
6.	I allow my child to skip classes if needed as long as he/she passes the requirements.	2.58	Agree
7.	I tell my child to not give up in their difficulties in school.	3.50	Strongly Agree
Overall Weighted Mean		3.22	Agree

Relatively, Oppermann et al. (2021) confirmed in their studies that parents' positive attitudes toward online learning can improve their involvement in their children's learning processes and online learning quality, which have a positive impact on students' academic outcomes.

Table 2. *Roles of Parents in Online Education: Monitoring*

<i>Roles of Parents in Online Education: Monitoring</i>		<i>Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
1.	I always monitor if my child's doing schoolwork on time.	3.30	Strongly Agree
2.	I inspect the results of his/her grade per subject every semester.	3.38	Strongly Agree
3.	I checked if my child is still listening to his/her teacher during online class.	3.27	Strongly Agree
4.	I get mad when I see my child play video games instead of doing schoolwork.	3.07	Agree
5.	I implement regulations inside our house.	3.31	Strongly Agree
6.	I pay attention to my child's mood and behavior at home.	3.36	Strongly Agree
7.	I enforce consequences fairly and consistently whenever he/she breaks the rules.	3.27	Strongly Agree
Overall Weighted Mean		3.28	Strongly Agree

The table shows the extent of the roles of parents in online education in terms of monitoring, and it gained an overall weighted mean of 3.28 verbally interpreted as Strongly Agree. This finding reveals that after PTC, parents were able to monitor their children especially the whenever there are opportunities to see their grades. These parents became also attentive to their children's mood and behavior.

According to Yu et al. (2012), parents who closely monitor their children can effectively monitor the nature of their computer use. Lee and Chae (2007), however, discovered that parents' active involvement also had positive effects.

Table 3. *Roles of Parents in Online Education: Academic Involvement*

<i>Roles of Parents in Online Education: Academic Involvement</i>		<i>Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
1.	I help my child with his homework.	3.03	Agree
2.	I help my child focus on one task at a time.	3.32	Strongly Agree
3.	I wake him/her up every morning to get ready for online class.	3.28	Strongly Agree
4.	I help my child in organizing his/her daily routine.	3.32	Strongly Agree
5.	I participated in school tasks that needed parents' involvement.	3.30	Strongly Agree
6.	I arrange the required devices and tools for learning before online class started.	3.39	Strongly Agree
7.	I provide my child assistance with the subjects he/she finds difficult.	3.32	Strongly Agree
Overall Weighted Mean		3.28	Strongly Agree

The table shows the extent of the roles of parents in online education in terms of academic involvement, and it gained an overall weighted mean of 3.28 verbally interpreted as Strongly Agree. The findings suggest that the learners are highly dependent on their parents' assistance and provision of resources and equipment required before the class started.

Silinskas and Kikas (2019) confirmed the existence of mixed results with respect to the research on the efficiency of parental involvement in homework on children's academic performance.

Table 4. *Roles of Parents in Online Education: Collaboration with School*

<i>Roles of Parents in Online Education: Collaboration with School</i>		<i>Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
1.	I ask his/her teacher/s about his progress and participation in school.	3.38	Strongly Agree
2.	I attend parent educational seminars to know practical strategies and ideas for learning.	3.32	Strongly Agree
3.	I communicate with my child's teachers to help him/her learn and succeed academically.	3.49	Strongly Agree
4.	I attend PTA meetings.	3.31	Strongly Agree
5.	I learn what the school offers.	3.39	Strongly Agree
6.	I always let the school know about my concerns.	3.19	Agree
Overall Weighted Mean		3.35	Strongly Agree

The table presents the extent of the roles of parents in online education in terms of collaboration with school. It garnered an overall weighted mean of 3.35, verbally interpreted as Strongly Agree. This finding suggests that parents became more active in communicating

with the school, especially to the teachers about the progress and needs of their children.

Montgomery and Goodall (2014) found out that some schools continue to place more emphasis on persuading parents to support school policy than on empowering parents to support the development of school policy and assisting them in participating in their children's education at home.

Table 5. *Roles of Parents in Online Education: Motivation*

<i>Roles of Parents in Online Education: Motivation</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
1. I encourage my child to complete all the school requirements.	3.59	Strongly Agree
2. I tell my child to pursue schooling.	3.59	Strongly Agree
3. I pressure my child to accomplish something everyday.	3.50	Strongly Agree
4. I give him/her rewards for their accomplishments.	3.01	Agree
5. I demonstrated a positive view of education at home.	3.42	Strongly Agree
6. I teach my child to stress awareness.	3.45	Strongly Agree
7. I provide timely and useful feedback about his/her class assignments and contributions to discussion.	3.45	Strongly Agree
Overall Weighted Mean	3.43	Strongly Agree

The table indicates the extent of the roles of parents in online education in terms of motivation. It garnered an overall weighted mean of 3.43, verbally interpreted as Strongly Agree. In terms of the students' motivation and learning results, the parents notice that they are unmotivated, have a hard time keeping up with the fast-paced instructions, are unable to complete the expected outputs, and have health-related issues.

According to Blaskova et.al (2019), sustainable academic motivation is the motivating interaction between fundamental concepts, viability, and fundamental academic motivational elements.

Reasons for Learners' Poor Performance

Home-related Factors

Since the respondents are sharing experiences they had during pandemic, when they were confined at home, learners needed to deal with their family-relationships. Thus, the first initial code generated is Family-relationship Problem" and the second generated code is Low Parental Support. These codes were elicited from the statements of participant 1, "*sa mother side lang po ako nagsstay*", participant 2, "*mama ko nalang po ang kasama ko*", participant 5, "*yung papa kopo during that time sa ibang bahay na po umuuwi*", and participant 10, "*kulang rin po ma'am sa supporta ng magulang*". Also, findings shows that the responsibilities between and among school, home and finances were jumbled because teachers have no control over what the students are doing during their class schedules. Thus, students' other responsibilities such as Household Chores and Work are the third and fourth codes. These are evident in the statements from participant 2, "*...tapos sumasabay yung trabaho ko sa DiviMart*", participant 7, "*naghanap po kasi ako ng work nun*", participant 8, "*madaming ginagawa sa bahay*", "*pinagtitinda kasi nila ako sa labasan*", and participant 15, "*...tapos nag-aalaga pa ako ng baby ko*".

In the study of Brian (2019), Family issues are revealed to have significant impact on kids' academic achievement, particularly on their attendance and performance.

Lack of Resources

Strong internet connection and functional gadget like cell phone or tablet play crucial roles in online learning. Therefore, problems for not having them greatly affect the learners' performances. So, the fifth generated code is No/ poor Internet Connection. It is also the most reoccurring answer from the participants: Participant 1, "*Nasa Laguna po kasi ako nun (walang internet)*", participant 2, "*...wala pa po kaming internet nun tapos nakiki-piso wifi eh sobrang hina po ng wifi*", participant 4, "*nawalang po ng internet...mahina po yung signal, looban po kasi yung amin*". Similar responses were also given by participants 6, 7, 8, and 10. The sixth code is parallel to poor internet connection which is Lack of Gadget taken from the responses of participant 4, "*dahil sa kakulangan ng budget at kagamitan*", and participant 7, "*di po kakayanin ng budget naming (bumili ng cellphone)*".

The pressure on the country's educational system is primarily due to the high cost of data, sharing of devices with siblings or parents, lack of interaction during class, and the inability of education assessment systems to effectively monitor student progress and identify learning losses (Cruz, 2022).

Leisure as distraction

Another highly recurrent answers from the respondents are Online Gaming/Sports which is the seventh generated code. Participant 1 said "*nawalan po ako ng oras kakalaro ng online games and anime*", Participant 3 said "*medyo napalaro po at napabarkada sa mga volleyball player*", Participant 13 said "*yung atensyon kopo talaga nakafocus sa paglalaro, honestly*", and other participants such of participant 9, 11, 12 and 14. This statement of participant 3 "*medyo napalaro po at napabarkada sa mga volleyball player*" can also be used for the eighth code Peer Influence which is supported by participant 11, who made mention of the following factors why

he failed to comply to his requirements: “*barkada, games, social media.*” Because of this, social media was also considered as the ninth code by the researchers.

The findings of Filade’s (2019) study showed that undergraduate students’ academic performance is significantly influenced by their peer group. According to Maria Luz Estudillo interviewed by CNN Philippines (2020), removing distractions at home during school time can greatly improve a student’s blended learning experience.

Learning Behavior and Attitude

Student monitoring has also been difficult for teachers because of their physical distance. Moreover, students had greater freedom to do what they want on their own time that led them to Laziness/Absenteeism. This tenth code was extracted from participant 3, “*di ko talaga alam ano mga napag-usapan sa klase dahil di na ako naka-attend*”, and participant 14 “*...di ako gumagawa ng mga pinapagawa ni ma’am*”. In addition, other psychological factors such as Poor Self-Esteem and Lack of Motivation were apparent among the students’ responses, thus, the eleventh and twelfth codes. Poor self-esteem was manifested in participant 3 “*Nagkamali lang po kasi ako sa sagot about sa recitation...parang naiyak kasi po lahat-lahat po sila pinagtatawanan yung sagot ko*”, participant 7 “*di ko sya kayang masagutan ng hindi sakin nae-explain ng maayos yung mga nandun...*”, and participant 9 “*...feeling ko din naman wala na akong pag-asa pumasa.*”. While Lack of motivation was expressed by participant 3, “*nawalan na rin po ako ng gana*” and participant 9 “*di ko rin po talaga feel ang online class, nakakatamad po*”. Lastly, Poor Time Management Skill is the thirteenth code. Though this code was implied by different students, Participant 3 explained “*...so minsan yung schedule po naming, umaga po talaga...Late na nakakatulog...late napo kami nagigising... minsan nakakatulog po ako sa room (zoom)...pagpasa ko minsan late na po...*” and participant 10 mentioned “*...hindi po nagagawa sa tamang oras*”.

Behavior and attitude of students in the new normal perspectives have an impact in their learning process. It contributes to self-determination in the new normal classes and framework theory of learning engagement and supports the influence of the new normal classes and learning perspective development (Mallillin, 2022). In addition, according to Sparks (2010), absenteeism has an impact on students’ learning ability, which can lead to lower grades, learner failure, and in some situations, grade repetition.

Effects of Parent-Teacher Conference as perceived by learners

Feelings

The first code Fear and Regret was manifested from the statements of participant 3, “*...nanghihinayang po kasi ako sa investment of time; natakot po akong bumagsak nun*”, participant 13, “*gusto ko parin naman po talaga makapagtapos kasi kuya ko po...walang trabaho*” and Participant 1, 2, 10, and 15 also gave responses that are alike. The second code is Motivation. The following statements of the participants show the effects of PTC to their motivation in various levels. For instance, Participant 11 said, “*mas na-motivate po ako, na-encourage, ganun*” which implies high motivation; however, Participant 4 said, “*bumawi nalang sa susunod*”, which implies low motivation. This code also appeared from the responses of participant 10, 12 and 13. The third generated code is Ashamed was elicited from participant 5, “*I was hesitant nap o talaga to respond din kay ma’am kasi nahihiya po ako eh; minsan hindi ko po binubuksan message nya*”, and participant 7, “*...kahit gustuhin ko po, hindi ko po talaga kaya...*”.

Seltzer (as cited by Milosevic, 2019) observes that occasionally, our fears of failing or being rejected paralyze us. He claims that after processing and learning from those experiences, you’ll be inspired to be vigilant about avoiding repeating that behavior in the future.

Actions

After the conduct of Parent-Teacher Conference, some of the learners improved as they decided to comply with the needed requirements. Participant 3 stated, “*...gumawa na ako, pinasa ko po lahat ng diko nagawa, pinasa ko na yung mga pt, mga activities...*”, and participant 11 stated “*mas naging productive pero hindi pressure, nag goal nalang po ako na pumasa.*”. Participants 8, 13 and 14 gave related answers too. From these responses, the fourth theme Complied. Additionally, participant 8 stated “*Unang-una po tinanggal ko po muna yung paglalaro ko ng online games; nag-comply po ako sa lahat ng kulang ko; ni-rush ko po lahat ng requirements na hindi ko pa naipapasa*”. this statement was used as a basis for the fifth code Removed Distraction. However, negative responses were also elicited from the participants. The sixth code Stopped was considered by the researchers, but they do not assume this as an effect of PTC, rather personal decisions of the respondents that are already out of the teachers’ control. The following responses conveyed that the participants voluntarily dropped out from school: participant 1, “*...nagpa-stop nalang po muna ako non, di ko na po kasi mahahabol.*” and participant 6, “*Alam ko na po talaga na babagsak ako kasi bago pa po mag-enrolment nagplano na ko mag-stop nagulat nalang po ako na-enroll po pala ako*”. Participant 2, 7 and 8 also provided similar answers.

Ajjawi (2019) discovered the factors that contributed to persistence and how students changed as a result of academic failure through an online poll with students who had failed yet persisted. Thematic analysis revealed that the majority of students sought peer, family, and friend assistance instead of institutional support after academic failure.

Relationship with Parents

The seventh code disappointed was articulated by participant 4, “*...nagalit sakin yung magulang ko...*” and participant 12, “*nalungkot po sila pero wala naman po silang magagawa kundi supportahan nalang ako*”. The eight code supportive was determined by the

following excerpts from participant 3, “*sinusupportahan din po nila ako na matapos mga gawain ko*”, and participant 11, “*Wala naman pong expectations ang parents ko, need ko lang daw po pumasa. Hindi sila naghigpit at naging understanding*”. The ninth code motivated was identified from the responses of participant 4, “*...pinagbabawalan na nila ako sa mga ginagawa ko...pagdalo sa pagpupulong sa Iglesia...volleyball*” and participant 15, “*...lagi po syang nagpapayo sa akin...; lagi nya po sinasabi na nanjan sya palagi kapag kailangan namin sya*”. The tenth code Set Limitations showed that parents adjusted some of their ways to help the learners focus in their studies, this is reflected in the statements of participant 4, “*...pinagbabawalan na nila ako sa mga ginagawa ko...pagdalo sa pagpupulong sa Iglesia...volleyball*” and participant 13, “*Tapos pinagbawalan ako na gumamit ng mga gadgets, sa umaga nalang*”. The eleventh code Monitoring reveals that parents also checked their children so that they can be catch-up with their lapses from school. This is evident in the statements of participant 3, “*...lagi po akong sinasabihan ng parents ko na kung nakapag-comply napo ako*”, and participant 13, “*Binabantayan po ako kapag no activities or wala akong ginagawa pinapagalitan*”. However, the last code No changes or accepted conveys that some other parents simply accepted their children’s shortcomings or did not modify their approach to their children despite being notified about the learners’ status. This was reflected Participant 1, “*Di naman po ako pinaghigpitan or pinagbawalan, pinagsabihan lang.*”, and Participant 7, “*wala naman na po sya magagawa*”.

American Psychological Association (2022) explains that having the child's best interests in mind while also being present, involved, and supportive is what it means to be a supportive parent.

Problems Encountered by the Teachers during the Conduct of Parent-Teacher Conference

Home-related Factors

The first theme is Home-Related Factors”. The most emerging code is Work which was evident from the answers of participant 5, “*...since may work yung parents kahit anong chat mo kahit anong message mo, tawagan mo out of coverage...*” and participant 8, “*...yung availability nila...laging mga dahilan, may trabaho...*”. Other codes such as Physical Conditions, said participant 6, “*...physical condition...senior citizen...*” and participant 14, “*...sila yung estudyante na may problema sa pamilya kadalasan...*”. Finally is Parental Duties code which was evident from the responses of participant 14, “*...may trabaho...buntis o may inaalagaang maliit na anak...*” and participant 15, “*...sa magulang...hindi nakikikooperate...maraming dahilan kung bakit hindi sila makapunta...may pupuntahan sila...may bata, walang magbantay, may trabaho...*”.

Finders and Lewis (2022) discussed that many parents find it difficult to participate because of their own educational background. Parents who did not finish school lack confidence in school meetings.

Lack of Interest

The second theme is Lack of Interest. The leading code among the answers of the participants is Not Responsive based on the responses of participant 1, “*...may mga bata at magulang talaga na hindi na sila paparamdamam sa gc, sa messenger...*” and participant 7, “*...yung ibang mga magulang hindi pa nagseseen sa gc...nagriring lang hindi na sinasagot...*”. Following is the Uncooperative code which can be found in the responses of participant 2, “*...hindi talaga nagcomply with agreement...*” and participant 6, “*...inaasa pa nila mga teachers yung mga ganon klase ng rules...*”. Last is Not Attending, which is gained from the answers of participant 3, “*...monitoring of attendance...sa attendance lang present...sa mismong klase hindi...*”, and participant 13, “*...hindi lahat nakakapunta...*”.

Some teachers perceive minority parents as not having time, interest, money, or energy to support classroom learning so they bypass them thinking they are helping them by not bothering them (Savacool, 2011).

Lack of Resources

The third theme is Lack of Resources. First is code under this theme is Out of Reach which is evident from the responses of participant 1, “*...unattended din ang kanilang ano..ang kanilang cellphone number na binibigay...*”. 14. Then the code Time Consuming was obtained from participant 4, “*...limited yung napupuntahan...*” and participant 6, “*...sobrang time consuming kase hinde concern mo lang concern student mo lang or targets students mo lang yung ivivisit sumasama ka sa ibang teachers na merong ding vinivisit...*”. It was followed by Poor Internet Connection as revealed in the answers of participant 5, “*...yung internet connection yung number 1 problem...*” and participant 7, “*...wala daw talagang internet sa kanila...*”. Last is the code Load, which was generated from participant 9, “*...walang load...*”.

The pressure on the country's educational system is primarily due to the high cost of data, sharing of devices with siblings or parents, lack of interaction during class, and the inability of education assessment systems to effectively monitor student progress and identify learning losses (Cruz, 2022).

Dishonesty

The fourth theme is Dishonesty. The most formed code is related to Wrong Information which was extracted from participant 2, “*...nagsisinungaling...wala daw guardian...*” and participant 7, “*...Tapos may experience pa ako na actors. Nung una yung problema niya daw ay wala silang internet. Tapos nung nakuha na yung gustong makuha araw araw ng online...*”. Then the Pointing Finger,

which was gathered from participant 1, “...meron din magulang na parang isinisasi na nga sa teacher ang problema e isinisasi kasi nag pm saakin na...kinapitalize nya na trabaho ng teacher ako gumagawa...”.

In accordance with Selvaraj (2022) survey, 1 in 4 students lie to their parents. Students admitted to lying about other things as well, but for 24% of the students polled, lying about grades was the biggest deception. This is a cause for concern.

Teachers’ Perceived Effects of Parent-Teacher Conference in Compliance Rate and Passing Rate

Positive Effects

The first theme is Positive Effects. The first emerging code is Parents’ Active Participation which was evident from the following responses from participant 1, “...feel ko naging effective yun dahil matataranta ang magulang e at effective din yung pag mention sa gc...” and participant 8, “...takot din silang bumagsak yung anak nila...”. The next code is Realization on Parents and Students’ Needs which was derived from the responses of participant 7, “...mas nakilala ko tuloy yung bata kasi pumupunta nga sila dito dahil nga nagcocomply...”, “...naging positibo naman yung ano pagtugon nung magulang...”. The third code, Consistent Monitoring, was generated from the responses of participant 2, “...binantayan ng parents....awareness ng magulang sa status ng bata...”, participant 8, “...magulang...mas namonitor nila yung mga anak nila...” and participant 13, “...overall maganda kahit sa online namonitor ng magulang...”. Fourth is the Students’ Active Participation code which was obtained from the responses of participant 3, “...Effective...naiimprove...” and participant 5, “...effective naman siya may nag-iimprove naman... ginagawa din naman nila yung part nila once na kinausap mo sila once na hinome visit mo sila...”. Then the Understanding Rules code which was reflected from the answer of participant 7, “...na-clear yun sa isipan ng mga bata na hindi pinamimigay ang grades...”. The sixth code is Strengthens Communication and Relationship which was gained from the responses of participant 9, “...mas na-strengthen na yung communication natin tsaka relationship sa parent during pandemic...” and participant 15, “...kapag maayos din and parentskausap, masusolve talaga yung problema...”. Then the Parents’ Positive Response code as evident from the answer of participant 15, “...yung parents na nagpapasalamat dahil inaupdate sila at least nalaman nila kasi hindi nila alam yung ginagawa ng students...”. Lastly, the Increase Passing Rate code which was reflected from the responses of participant 9, “...nagkaroon naman ng magandang resulta yun...first sem parang 9 silang LARS then...end of the year may dalawa talagang hindi na nakaakyat...”.

Based on the study of Machumu (2015), there is a positive and significant relationship between parental involvement in the school activities and academic performance of their children.

Negative Effects

Different codes were drawn relative to the Negative Effects of Parent-Teacher Conference. The first code is Too Much Considerations which was gained from the responses of participant 4, “...ineffective kasi at the end of the day, ipapasa mo pa rin kasi ikaw ang masisisi, babalik sayo at ikaw magreremedial. and participant 15, “...first sem kung hindi talaga naging worth it yung intervention at walang pinagbago ang student hindi ko na talaga inenroll nung 2nd sem...”. Habitual Actions was obtained from the responses from participant 6, “...kaya sila lars kase hinde sila nag viview hinde sila nag oopen ng messenger” and participant 9, “...parang nasanay na parang hindi na nadala pati na rin sa parent hindi na natutuwa pati sya pinatawag na rin...”. The third code, Low Quality of Learners was extracted from participant 6’s answer, “...hinde ko masasabe na 100% effective...admit natin sarili natin totoo at nag eexist talaga na nag manipulate tayo ng data ibig sabihen yung mga bata na hinde naman talaga pasok sa standard, hinde naman talaga cocomply binibigyan ... minimum requirments na hinde na pasok sa competency para lang maipasa sila ...”. The last code, Blaming Teachers was obtained from participant 6, “...the teacher’s part lugi karin pag marami kang binagsak or marami kang hinde pinagbigyan kase yun nga ikaw yung masisi tatanongin ka ano yung nagawa mo tapos mababa yung rate na makukuha mo kase marami kang bagsak mapapalitan kapa...teachers times na foforce sya na ipasa yung mga estudyante kaya masasabi kona yung passing rate hinde sya basis for the effectiveness...”.

Machumu (2015) on his study affirmed this by stressing that school administrators and teachers face challenges related to reaching out to parents in positive ways, using strategies that will result in improved children academic achievement, and balancing the needs of parents and professional autonomy is a reliable option.

Teachers’ Recommendations for Parent-Teacher Conference

Teachers’ Involvement

Various codes were derived from the participants’ answers to the interview that are themed as Teachers’ Involvement. The first code generated from the extracts is Checklist which was evident from the responses of participant 1, “...ipopost din po ni teacher yung mga activities ...”, participant 7, “...dapat talaga sa guidance office mayroon na tayong list...”, and participant 9, “...nakalagay dun yung pangalan ng bata, yung checklist kung bakit ko sya pinatawag...”. The second code formed from the responses is Update. It is evident from the responses of participant 2, “...gc for parents...inform and update them sa activities from time to time...”, participant 7, “...Bago matapos ang school year, mapatawag ang magulang. Para at least makikita nila kung talagang karapat dapat yung bata, ...”, and participant 12, “...dapat ma-inform po sila before that na may nakaschedule na talaga na mapaghandaan ng parents...”. The third code is Meeting which can be seen from the responses of participant 3, “...Dapat mas madalas ang PTC...”, and participant 15, “...kapag may mga conference sinasabi natin status ng anak nila...para hindi tayo umabot sa...bigayan ng card...para maagapan na

natin...”. Then the Distribution of Report Card code which was generated from participant 13, “...isabay ang PTC sa food packs ...”. Finally, Consistent Communication Code which was obtained from participant 15, “...advice dapat ang teacher and adviser may communication para may consistency...”.

Parent-teacher meetings at schools and other interactions with teachers may increase accountability and transparency, which will enhance the quality of school services. (e.g., Kremer et al., 2013, Mbiti, 2016).

School Administration’s Support

Related codes about School Administration’s Support for Parent-Teacher Conference were drawn. Starting with the first emerging code, Firm Guidelines, drawn from the responses of participant 3, “...firm guidelines...di gaya ng nangyayari na end of quarter...” and participant 4, “...firm guidelines for LARs quality...”, participant 6, “...firm rules regarding ano LARS...”. The second code is Enrollment Limitations gained from participant 3, “...Extent for LARS...” and participant 9, “...Si guidance, si PTA, yung mga stakeholders regarding the PTC magkaroon ng isang kasunduan na may limitasyon ng pagpapatawag...tatlong beses...”. Third code is Revisit Curriculum Guide which was extracted from participant 4, “...unmet competency...curriculum is congested and not applicable sa lahat...”. Next is Limit Home Visitation, which was reiterated by participant 6, “...home visit...wag lang sya ioverdo kase pag inoverdo...”. Following is Service and Security as mentioned by participant 6, “...kung magka-conduct tayo ng home visit as much as possible sana merong service kase kaylangan yun ni teacher for the security ni teacher ...” and participant 12, “...home visitation...problema...kami po mismo ang pupunta na hindi namin masyado alam yung lugar. Maligaw-ligaw po kami...nauubos yung time...kung meron kaming masasakyan na maghahatid at sundo...”. Next code is Seminar and Program as suggested by participant 8, “...bigyan sila lahat ng chance...sa mga klase ng mga programa...mga seminar para sa parenting...school involvement...para alam nila yung responsibility nila...”. Then the Certified Guidance Counselor was suggested by participant 10, “...magkaroon pa tayo ng isa pang staff diba kase sila sir guidance may klase den ...”. Finally is the suggestion for Communication Allowance from participant 12, “...load... kasi wala ng load yung sim ko...”.

Teachers must hold intensive parenting seminar to the parents of academically at-risk students. Teachers are encouraged to understand students’ background by knowing their socio-demographic profile. It is suggested that home visits be done at the start before the school year begins to help the teachers find and have a better understanding of the various strengths and challenges faced by each student and to address their needs in achieving good grades (Gatilogo and Tan, 2019).

Parents’ Motivation

Different codes were represented by the theme Parents’ Motivation. The first is Parental Involvement Recognition which can be drawn from the answer of Participant 6, “...yung card yung parang parent teacher card...kase ano mas na momonitor doon individually yung performance nila ...parang somehow it’s a form of motivation sa kanila ...”. Then the Parent’s Report Card which was suggested by participant 8, “...parent’s report card...si parent may report card rin ng kanyang performance sa school...si estudyante, sya mismo magrirate sa parent nya para malaman natin yung involment nya...”.

Based on the recommendations of Gatilogo and Tan (2019) on their study, parents are encouraged to give and utmost support to their children’s education specially by being aware of their responsibilities.

Students’ Screening and Assessment

Codes related to Students’ Screening and Assessment are identified. To start with the first code, Screening that was evident from the recommendations of participant 1, “...you have to know the nature of your learner talaga and yung family background...hindi niya kayang maituro yung subject ko ...” and participant 4, “...accepting students...mag screen ng students...limit the accommodation...”. Following is the Students Information System as pointed out by participant 4, “...enrollment palang, may gc na agad hindi na hahanapin pa...” and participant 12, “...pwede pa rin naman po sanang gamitin text po ano, yung brigade...pwedeng tawagan...”. Lastly, Assessment as mentioned by participant 15, “...sa discussion kapag nagtuturo, ...dapat nating i-assess talaga yung bata kung may natutunan ba, magbigay ng assessment...upang malaman ba kung ang bata ay may natutunan...”.

Scheid (2019) mentioned that Students’ personal data are necessary for our educational system to improve student outcomes. Data are used by educators to enhance learning, empower parents and communities, and assist legislators in setting priorities and allocating resources.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of this study, the following are the conclusions drawn from the results of the study.

The themes that emerge on Teachers’ Techniques/Strategies Used to Conduct Parent-Teacher Consultation are categorized to the following themes and codes: (1) “Distance Communication” means the modes of communication utilized by the teachers to reach out the parents and students during online learning such as Messenger, Online Meeting, and Phone Call. (2) “Face-to-Face Meeting” where parents meet through Home Visitations, Personal Meetings, and Card Distribution”. (3) “Parent-Teacher Communication” pertains to sending letter of invitation such as call slip or calling the attention of parents through School Parent-Teacher Association, Guidance

Counselor, and other stakeholders. (4) “Teachers’ Intervention” is teacher’s other way of inviting the parents to come to school where they get the parents involved in conducting the intervention by asking them to supervise and monitor their children by complying to the given ultimatum and following the agreement between them and students.

Based on findings, conducting parent-teacher conferences for the Learners-at-Risk has affected the Roles of parents in the following terms: (1) Parents were able to show positive attitudes about online learning and model it to their children. They would want their children to have their outlook in online education to be similar to what they had face-to-face. That includes being positive despite the challenges they encounter in the new normal set-up. However, as consideration, it also appears that parents are more lenient when it comes to tardiness and absenteeism, as long as the learners are still able to submit necessary school requirements. (2) Parents were able to monitor their children especially whenever there were opportunities to see their grades. These parents became also attentive to their children’s mood and behaviour, however, still lenient to their leisure, specifically in the use of gadgets or playing mobile games. (3) Parents were also able to assist their children when it comes to their home routine such as, preparing their device, getting up for class, helping to focus and help them with their difficulties in school, but not directly get involved with their school works such as homework. (4) Parents were also perceived to be more active in communicating to school, especially to the teachers about the progress and needs of their children. However, it can also be perceived that they do not always raise all their concerns to the school. This shows that parents are still aware about the concerns that must only be within the bound of their home. (5) Parents also reinforced their children’s motivation by encouraging them to submit requirements and telling them the value of schooling, however, it doesn't give many rewards for their accomplishments.

The themes that emerged from the reasons for learners' poor performance were (a) Home-Related Factors, (b) Lack of Resources, (c) Leisure as Distraction, and (d) Learning Behaviour and Attitude.

The themes that emerged from the effects of Parent-Teacher Conference as perceived by learners were (a) Feelings, (b) Actions, and (c) Relationship with Parents.

The following themes formed based on Teachers’ Perceived Effects of Parent-Teacher Conference in Compliance Rate and Passing Rate are “Positive Effects” where the following codes were extracted: (a) Parents’ Active Participation, (b) Realizations on Parents and Students’ Needs, (c) Consistent Monitoring, (d) Student’s Active Participation, (e) Understanding of Rules, (f) Strengthens Communication and Relationship, (g) Parent’s Positive Response, and (h) Increase Passing Rate. “Negative Effects” is reflected to the following codes: (a) Too Much Considerations, (b) Habitual Actions, (c) Low Quality of Learners, and (d) Blaming Teachers.

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